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Ventral

Artematopidae: *Artematopus* sp.

Dorsal Artematopidae: *Artematopus* sp.

Artematopidae: *Artematopes* sp.

Artematopidae: *Artematopus* sp.

Elateridae: *Pseudotetralobus* sp.

Elateridae: *Pseudotetralobus* sp.

Cu branching primitive } primitive start!
 R₁ preserved

Elateridae: *Pseudotetralobus* sp.

Rhinorhipidae: *Rhinorhipus tamboriensis*

Rhinorhipidae: *Rhinorhipus* sp.

Eucnemidae: *Hemiopsida* sp.

Lampyridae: *Pterotus*?

Derodontidae: *Derodontus trisignatus*

Derodontidae: *Peltastica tuberculata*

CuP and claval line reduced

Ptinidae: Anobiinae: *Xeranobium* sp.

Sister of Bostrichidae?

Bostrichidae: *Bostrichopsis jesuita*

Bostrichidae: *Bostrichopsis jesuita*

Bostrichidae: *Bostrichopsis* sp.

Bostrichidae: *Bostrichopsis* sp.

Bostrichidae: *Endecatomus rugosus*

Bostricho.
Dermestidae: *Anthrenus* sp.

Dermestidae: *Anthrenus* sp.

window makes stronger bend possible

Dermeestidae: *Anthrenus* sp.

Bostricho.

Dermeestidae: *Attagenus pello*

Dermeestidae: *Dermeestes ater*

DORSAL

VENTRAL

Dermestidae: *Dermestes maculatus*

Dermeestidae: *Dermeestes maculatus*

Bostrichoidea
 Dermestidae: *Dermestes maculatus*

Bostrichoformia

Dermestidae: *Orphinus subnitidus*?

Nosodendridae: *Nosodendron unicolor*

Nosodendridae: *Nosodendron unicolor*

Nosodendridae: *Nosodendron unicolor*

Similar to Cleridae

Nosodendridae: *Nosodendron unicolor*

Nosodendron

Extended wing

Folded wing

Lymexylidae: *Atractocerus* sp.

ScP runs under RA
RP and MA reduced

Lymexylidae: *Melittoma* sp.

CuP and claval line reduced

Cleridae: *Eunatalis* sp.

Watch for
Strange Cut!

Cleridae:

Bishop Museum, Laos

Coleoptera apomorphies in hind wing articulation:

AX-PC & C (tegula) reduced; B-R partly membranized; F-M subdivided; B-M large, connected with B-Cu; AX-Cu (3Ax) small, sutured, and often fragmented; AX-Cu fused with F-Cu; F-Cu fused with FA

Melyridae: *Dicranolaius major*

close to Emdomyelidae
diff. larval head

Trogossitidae: *Lepidopteryx lacer*

Trogossitidae: *Eronyxa pallidus*

Possibly derived from eucinetoids

Cleroida
Trogossitidae: *Lepidopteryx moniliata*

Trogossitidae: *Lepidopteryx moniliata*

Trogossitidae: *Ostoma pippings*

